

Invariance, Information and the Maxwell-Boltzmann Factor?

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The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) probability factor $\exp(-.5mvv/T)$ where T is temperature may be derived through the time reversal reaction balance of elastic two body collisions i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$. The latter relation may be assumed a priori. Taking \ln of it and equating to the former multiplied by $-1/T$ yields the MB relation.

In this note we argue that this calculation may be thought of in terms of information. Even though $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ is assumed a priori and \ln taken to convert it into a sum, in information science $\ln(f(e_i))$ is called information. In physics, one may think of it in terms of a change relative to the value itself e.g. $d/dT \ln(f(e_1)) = df(e_1)/dT / f(e_1)$. Two body elastic collisions represent the interactions in the system, thus: $E=e_1+e_2= e_i+e_j$. In other words the only information before and after an interaction is a given E . We argue that equilibrium tries to minimize information so $f(e_1)$ and $f(e_2)$ together representing the collision e_1+e_2 should not represent any new information. Thus one expects $G(e_1+e_2)$ to represent this probability such that G splits into two identical parts. This may occur through addition or multiplication. Multiplication allows for $f(e_1)$ to drop to zero as $e_1 \rightarrow$ infinite. Thus we argue that an information type argument may lead to $G(e_1+e_2) = f(e_1)f(e_2)$ which in turn leads to the MB factor.

In the case of a potential we consider the idea of spatial invariance which already appears in Fermat's principle and is linked with conservation of momentum in the direction of an invariant variable. For no potential one clearly has spatial invariance of $.5mvv$. With a potential, one has spatial invariance of $E_1= .5mv(x)v(x) +V(x)$. Assuming invariance of this variable together with the loss of information from $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ one may suggest $f(E) = \exp(-(.5mvv+V(x))/T)$ ((A)). This begs the question: How does d/dx and conservation which appear in Fermat's principle due to spatial invariance appear here? We argue that d/dx , the generator of translations, is linked to spatial invariance. We again use the idea of equilibrium trying to minimize information. We use density $d(x)$, but write it as information i.e. $\ln(d(x))$ and argue that a change in this value should equal a change in a scalar given piece of information in the system namely $V(x)/T_1$ where T_1 is a constant to create proper units. This may alternatively be written with a d/dx as in Fermat's principle to create a conservation law i.e. $d/dx \ln(d(x)) = -d/dx V(x)/T_1$. This is equivalent to a pressure difference balanced by a force times density. Thus informational ideas may yield Newtonian mechanical balance.

Information considerations lead to $d(x) = \exp(-V(x)/T_1)$ so $d(x)$ vanishes for large x for say an oscillator potential. Using information minimization for a single point x i.e. $f(v) = \exp(-.5mvv/T)$ one may say that having $T_1=T$ yields spatial invariance for the total energy over x as suggested in ((A)).

Thus we argue that ideas of minimization of information together with invariance may be key to obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor and may also account for the Newtonian pressure -force*density "conservation".

Maxwell-Boltzmann Factor Without a Potential - Reaction Balance

The MB factor, in the absence of a potential, may be derived using time reversal balance of two body elastic scattering i.e.

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad e_i = .5m v(i)v(i) \quad ((1b))$$

((1a)) represents the definition of energy conservation, but ((1b)) is sometimes introduced a priori as representing the probability of an e_1 and e_2 colliding. Taking \ln of ((1b)) and linking to ((1a)) with a multiplicative factor $-1/T$ yields $\ln(f(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ or $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((2)) i.e. the MB factor.

No mention of information has been made in the above approach. We argue, however, that information minimization appears implicitly. The form $\ln(f(e_i))$ is by definition information in information science. In physics one may argue that this form ensures that a change due to a single derivative e.g. d/dT is divided by the original value i.e. $d/dT \ln(f(e_i)) = df/dT / f$.

This represents a relative change as opposed to an absolute.

In an elastic collision $E = e_1 + e_2$ before the reaction and $E = e_i + e_j$ after. Thus the specific e_1 and e_2 values merge to produce an E . This is the only information needed for an elastic collision. If information minimization is to hold for equilibrium (an assumption) then $f(e_1)$ and $f(e_2)$ which are also pieces of information (and can be changed) in the system should combine to form a function $G(E)$ which represents the probability for an e_1 to react with an e_2 . Furthermore $G(E)$ should be represented by two equal functions. This may be done though:

$$G = b(e_1 + e_2) \quad \text{i.e.} \quad f(e) = be \quad \text{or} \quad G = f(e_1)f(e_2) \quad ((3))$$

$f(e) = be$ does not drop to zero for high e , but increases which is unphysical, so $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ is chosen. This must contain the same information as $e_1 + e_2$ so taking \ln of $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ and equating it together with a multiplicative factor $-1/T$ inserted yields the MB distribution.

One may note that for a system with noninteracting particles with energies e_1 and e_2 and some fixed $f(e_1)$ and $f(e_2)$ such that the particles elastically bounce off of a wall (a Newtonian picture) there is no interaction to minimize the information. Thus e_1 and $f(e_1)$ are two independent pieces of information. If an interaction is introduced it cannot change e_1 , but can modify $f(e_1)$. We suggest that minimization of information is at work.

We also note that in the case of no potential (or a constant potential) there is spatial invariance.

MB Distribution With a Potential

Consider now a gas in a 1-D box with a potential $V(x)$. We make use of the idea of spatial invariance of total energy i.e.

$$E = .5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) \quad ((4))$$

In other words if one has E at x_1 and E at x_2 then one does not have any extra probabilistic information. Thus $f(.5mvv) = \exp(-.5mvv/T)$ becomes:

$$f(E) = \exp(-.5mvv/T + V(x)/T) \quad ((5))$$

At any given x , the two body result without a potential holds i.e. $\exp(-.5mvv/T)$. In this case, instead considering elasticity $e_1+e_2 = E$ one considers $.5mvv + V = E$. $V(x)$ takes the place of e_2 in the conservation equation. One may have an $f(\text{energy related to } v)$ and $f(\text{energy related to } x)$ and obtain ((5)) in exactly the same manner that one obtained $\exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T)$ for no potential.

Thus the idea of both invariance and information minimization come into play.

Considering the Factor $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ and Information

One may apply the idea of minimization of information to $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ alone, we argue. We suggest that if $V(x)=0$ there is uniform density, but with $V(x)$ there is a density $d(x)$ which (if normalized) is like a probability. We consider a change in space to be generated by d/dx (the translational operator) and consider a relative change as representing information:

$$\text{i.e. } \ln(d(x)) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is a scalar. We seek another scalar of information about x namely $V(x)$. (It is possible to create derivatives of $V(x)$, but $-dV/dx$ is a vector, namely force, and higher derivatives are also vectors.) Thus to minimize information in the x direction we suggest:

$$\ln(d(x)) = -V(x)/T_1 \text{ where } T_1 \text{ is a scalar so units are fine} \quad ((7))$$

This leads to $d(x) = C \exp(-V(x)/T_1)$. This may be compared with $C_2 \exp(-.5mvv/T)$ with no potential. If $C=C_2$ and $T=T_1$ one obtains a result which depends on $E = .5mvv+V(x)$ which is invariant in x i.e. the overall MB distribution ((5))

Fermat's Principle

We try to argue that the above ideas using invariance are similar to the result of Fermat's principle of least time applied to light e.g. reflection/refraction. Formally this approach extremizes the sum of time for each ray. The details, however, show that if the mirror or medium flat surface is along x at $y=0$ then there is a constraint in the y direction, but not in the x direction. Thus there is spatial invariance in the x direction so x may be varied. We argue that spatial invariance is linked with a conserved quantity. In this case it is (p_x) momentum in the x direction. In the MB case $E = .5mvv+V(x)$ was a conserved quantity introducing a kind of spatial invariance. We will argue later, however, that there is a second conservation law at work.

In Fermat's principle, $\text{time} = \text{distance}/\text{speed}$. For refraction, $\text{speed} = c/n_1$ and c/n_2 for each ray and $d_1 = \sqrt{(x-x_a)^2 + (y-0)^2}$ and $d_2 = \sqrt{(x_b-x)^2 + (y-0)^2}$ Here $(0, y_a)$ is the initial point and (x_b, y_b) the final. Varying x i.e. taking $d/dx (t_1+t_2) = 0$ shows that there is spatial invariance and

leads directly to $(p_1x) = (p_2x)$ for refraction where $(p_1x) = p n_1 \sin(\theta_1)$ and $(p_2x) = p n_2 \sin(\theta_2)$. Thus taking d/dx leads to a conservation law and indicates spatial invariance.

Application to the MB Case

In the MB situation with a potential we argued that: $\ln(d(x)) = -V(x)/T$. This holds for any x so there is spatial invariance. This is similar to $t_1(x) + t_2(xb-x)$. This is also spatially invariant because one may shift the two rays in the x -direction without really changing the situation.

We suggest taking d/dx to see if a conservation law appears as in Fermat's case:

$$d/dx \ln(d(x)) = -1/T \quad dV/dx \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is Newton's pressure-force*density balance assuming Pressure $V = nRT$ i.e. the ideal gas law. Thus we suggest that information minimization and spatial invariance may lead to this result.

Conclusion

In conclusion we suggest that in an equilibrium situation the system (interactions) may change a variable piece of information such as $f(e_1)$ (number of particles with e_1) or $d(x)$ (density). These are similar to a probability and we suggest writing them as information i.e. $\ln(f(e_1))$ and $\ln(d(x))$ so that first derivative changes to this information yields an absolute change over the value itself i.e. $d/dT \ln(f(e_1)) = df/dT / f$. We suggest that given fixed information about the system e.g. $e = .5mvv$ or $V(x)$, the interactions present act on the variable information pieces to equate them up to a multiplicative constant to the existing information $e_1, V(x)$ which cannot be changed. We also suggest that spatial invariance in the system helps to minimize information. Spatial invariance is linked to the translational operator d/dx which may be applied to create conservation equations as in Fermat's principle. We suggest that it may be used to create Newton's balance of pressure with force*density where $PV=nRT$ i.e. the ideal gas law.